

Factors influencing the Effectiveness of online Content marketing in Bangladesh

Siyam-E-Nur & Md Awlad Hossain

Abstract

The goal of this research was to look at some of the aspects that might affect the success of online content marketing in Bangladesh. The data for this study was acquired using online questionnaires and includes 103 respondents from diverse demographics. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics, ANOVA analysis, and a regression model in this associative, inferential, and predictive study. The findings revealed that the attitude of Bangladeshi consumers towards online content marketing was overall positive and accepting. The overall findings also revealed that Bangladeshi consumers hold a more favorable attitude towards online content marketing and the independent variables - "producing quality content," "understanding obscure demands," and "customers' attitude towards CM" are significant (p -value < 0.05) In addition, these three variables, "quality content," "obscure demands," and "customer attitude," have a positive relationship with the dependent variable. So, it can be claimed that a change in the quality of content that the companies produce, a change in the companies' ability to understand the customers' obscure demands, and a change in the customers' attitude towards content marketing as a whole will significantly affect the effectiveness of online content marketing in Bangladesh. According to the findings, if local and multinational companies want to gain an advantage in overcoming the challenges of bringing effectiveness to their online content marketing, they should produce high-quality content, try to understand customers' obscure needs, and increase their positive attitude toward content marketing.

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1. Introduction

Utilizing content as a marketing tool is widely popular among international and local businesses. Content marketing focuses on generating solid content, publishing them, and persuading customers to achieve the intended objectives. For many years marketing messages given through visual contents are a broadly accepted strategy to catch the attention of the desired market segments. Świeczak (2012) noted that these days content marketing is not just something desirable, rather it is a must-have branch of marketing. But though content marketing is very popular in practice, in the scientific research area this is still a quite new thing. Only a few authors provided solid academic information to have a good theoretical understanding of content marketing (Repoviene & Pazeraite, 2016).

Throughout the world, numerous business organizations are already using online platforms to reach their audience through regular activities. For example, 60% of the marketing budget of Kelly Services, an international recruitment firm based in the USA, is consumed by content making and distribution works (Kelly Services, 2015). As time is shifting, more and more organizations are realizing the importance of content marketing. Along with the rest of the world, the practice is also present in Bangladesh. Almost all the internet users and specifically social media users are always encountering numerous online advertisements and marketing tools featured with different visual contents like images, videos, data-driven charts, and so on. A huge number of online and offline-based large and small companies are seen to have their websites and social media pages, from where they publish various content targeting their target groups. But the question remains that, despite having this kind of large attention and focus, how much effective content marketing is being in the context of Bangladesh.

Today we live in a world where the internet has become an extremely common platform for communication and entertainment. Smartphones along with internet facilities are now available at a lower price than ever. As a result, the internet has become a platform of great interest for business organizations too. The heavy usage of social media among different types of people is another common scenario. The regular presence of almost all types of people has forced the business organizations to try hard to become creative with social media platforms for conducting their marketing activities. Such platforms include Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Pinterest, and so on. Also, other types of online marketing activities on different websites are still very popular among business organizations. These online activities often heavily rely on visual content.

Textual, visual or aural contents that can be found on the web fall into the category of online content. Online visual contents may include images, videos, infographics, diagrams, charts, presentation slides, and so on. As visual contents fit very well with online platforms like social media and other typical websites, content marketing has become widely popular among businesses to create their online presence. Pullizi (2010) claimed that using content as a marketing tool is not something new. Rather, images, data-driven figures, graphs, and charts are being used as marketing tools for a long time. They are still present in books, newspapers, magazines, and published materials. But the introduction of online content has given businesses a great chance to reach more specific target markets with their contents than those traditional channels. As a result, the marketing strategies of today's organizations have also changed. From being one-way communications, marketing strategies have changed into two-way communications, and that was the flourish of content marketing (Patruti Baltes, 2015). Sometimes, content marketing is also referred to as story marketing (Sullivan, 2013). Odden (2013) stated that this specialized marketing adds value to the customer and thus enhances

the purchasing process. Also, content marketing is changing the field of marketing by even changing the job description of marketers by transforming them into publishers (Pulizzi, 2012). Zero Moment of Truth, a project of Google introduced in 2011, discovered that from 2010 to 2011, the number of contents viewed by average consumers has increased from 5 pieces to 10 pieces. (Lecinski, 2014). Again, user-generated contents motivate users in crowdsourcing, contributes ideas to brands, and provides valuable information to other users (Neiburger, 2010). A great advantage of content marketing is its ability to provide business entities with a great opportunity to position their brands or products or services. Today, marketers are making and publishing good content which can help them to reinforce their positioning. It is unprecedented that the future of marketing is looking not like marketing at all, but like publishing (Gagnon, 2014).

We are living in a world where most parts of the earth are connected through the internet and internet-enabled mobile handsets. As a result, business organizations are trying their best to utilize mobile and internet platforms to communicate with their target markets and to promote their brand, products, services, and so on. Along with the whole world, the business entities of Bangladesh are also being seen to be heavily involved with the online platforms. From small startups to large corporations, whether rural or urban, are trying to establish their online presence. Through this, rival businesses are consistently trying to catch the attention of internet users. So, content marketing with the help of various appealing visual contents is on the rise. Though content marketing is getting so much importance and focus in Bangladesh, the number of researches on this topic is very few. This research can help to fill the gap and can provide a real picture to the business-people about the effectiveness of their efforts. Also, through the findings of the research, businesses may get hints about where things are going wrong and where to put their attention more. Therefore, the main objective of the study is to investigate the effectiveness of online visual content and its marketing in Bangladesh. The current study also has some specific objectives (i) to recognize the demographic factors that influence online visual content marketing effectiveness, (ii) to explore and demonstrate the actual condition of content marketing in Bangladesh, and (iii) To specify the significant factors that impact the online visual content marketing.

2. Literature review

2.1 Online visual contents, it's marketing and effectiveness

Effectiveness has been defined in many ways and perhaps one of the most precise definitions was given by Erlendsson (2002). He defined effectiveness as “the extent to which objectives are met (‘doing the right things’).” According to Handley and Chapman (2011, p. 21), content denotes “anything created and uploaded to a website: the words, images, or other things that reside here”. Again, by focusing on the users (and potential customers) of companies' websites, Halvorson and Rach (2012, p. 13) mentioned that content denotes “what the user came to read, learn, see, or experience (in a website)”. So, we can say that online or web contents are like the building blocks of what we see, hear, or experience in the websites and related internet-based platforms. Also, it is clear from the proposed definitions that the contents of a website can be textual, visual, or aural. In this study, we are only concerned about those online visual contents that are used to conduct content marketing. So, their effectiveness according to Erlendsson's (2012) definition will happen if the objective of their production is fulfilled, which is the effectiveness of content marketing. So, the research is focused mainly on the effectiveness of content marketing. The term content marketing has been defined in different ways by different sources. Content Marketing Institute (CMI, 2017, p.1) defined this term as "a strategic marketing approach focused on creating and distributing valuable, relevant, and consistent

content to attract and retain a clearly-defined audience – and, ultimately, to drive profitable customer action". Again, content marketing was defined as "a management process where enterprises identify, analyze, and satisfy customers' demand of gaining profits with the use of digital content distributed through electronic channels (Rowley, 2008)". Here, if we look at the two definitions, we find that both of the definitions have common understandings. That is, content marketing focuses on using suitable content as a tool to serve the customers to earn a profit. Now, interestingly the definition of marketing according to Kotler & Armstrong (2012, p.52) also conveys the same thing, that is "the process by which companies create value for the customers and build strong customer relationships to capture value from them in return". So, it can also be said that content marketing is not completely different from traditional marketing. Rather, it is just a new way to do marketing to achieve the same objectives with some new tools through web platforms. And apparently, content marketing also shares similar objectives of mainstream marketing. Thus, it should be designed within the companies' main and overall marketing strategy.

It has also been claimed that content marketing mostly resembles inbound marketing that pulls customers to the company's products and services by offering useful information and resources (Steenburgh et al. 2011). According to Smith and Chaffey (2013), the web is a pull marketing environment and, in this environment, companies pull customers to their brand websites. Holliman and Rowley (2014) stated that content is a crucial component of inbound marketing techniques, and so understanding of how content can be used in marketing, or more specifically, in engaging customers, is the focal point of developing an effective inbound marketing approach. Also, Halligan and Shah (2010) mentioned that there is a progressive interest in the potential of pull or inbound digital marketing in which customers and prospects actively search out brands that provide engaging and valuable content that is relevant to their needs. In pull marketing, the company enjoys greater authority over its market than push marketing and it can also be engaging, attractive, and rich. So, the reasons for the popularity of content marketing is easily understandable. Świeczak (2012) stated that content marketing enables the real commitment of the target group and creates an authentic, honest relationship with the group, based on trust and partnership. He further mentioned that content marketing is the only branch of marketing, in which the message, which is commercial in form, has such a strong potential that it makes target consumers look actively for this message. These statements express the strong potential that content marketing possesses.

Online based Content marketing has been present in Bangladesh for a couple of years. Though several studies have been conducted on this topic by various researchers internationally, the number of studies in the case of Bangladesh is very few. The number of published researches from Bangladesh is also very few. So, this study tries to fill the gap by bringing out the real picture of online content that is being published by various business entities targeting their existing and potential customers. Also, it aims to fill the gap by trying to remove the ambiguity that surrounds the Bangladeshi content marketers about its usefulness in the case of Bangladesh. Along with international business sectors, content marketing has also become a must for Bangladeshi businesses. Both the local and multinational companies are trying to utilize this flourishing branch of marketing. So, it is expected that the fulfillment of the gaps will help the businesses to build their content marketing strategies in a better way.

2.2 AIDA Model and Its Relation to the Effectiveness of Content Marketing

E. St. Elmo Lewis proposed the theory of communication called the AIDA (Attention, Interest, Desire, and Action) model in 1898. Though a long time has passed, this model is so extensive

that, Ashcroft and Hoey (2001) stated, this model can be applied to Internet services as it is applied to other products and services. And perhaps one of the most explicit acknowledging statements about this applicability was given by Michaelson and Stacks (2011). They mentioned that, though we live in a world of interactive online communication and social networks, users still need to be aware of the existence of a product, show interest in the product based on information related to the benefits, and express a desire to possess the products because they meet the needs, wants, and their interests, and take action to decide to purchase or other relevant actions. Rose and Pulizzi (2011) identified the objectives of content marketing, they stated them as brand awareness or reinforcement; lead conversion and nurturing; customer conversion; customer service; customer upsell; and passionate subscribers. Interestingly, these objectives are very similar to the objectives of advertising in digital media and that is perhaps a result of their closely similar foundations. So, for the convenience of conducting research that is suitable for the Bangladeshi markets, the well-known AIDA (Attention, Interest, Desire, and Action) model can be used to measure the effectiveness of online visual contents and its marketing. This model has widely been applied in marketing activities both in online and traditional methods. Also, it is often referred to as a marketing communication model and in formulating marketing strategies (Hassan et al. 2015).

Figure 1: AIDA MODEL

2.3 Variables

Reaching the Right Audience

When it comes to contents, the companies publish them targeting someone. If it does not or cannot reach them, then the objective is not fulfilled accordingly. Many times, users experience the contents of totally irrelevant sources. Which indicates that the money and the attention that the companies are pouring in, may not be bringing effectiveness in their content marketing activities. Wong & Yazdanifard (2015) stated from another source that in most cases multinational companies participate in content marketing activities and they try to adapt their messages to target the right audience when doing business globally.

Bringing Personalization

Personalization denotes tailoring the contents' messages so that they match with the different groups of people's individualistic characteristics. The number of customers who wish to get personalized customer experiences that represent personal needs, attitudes, and situations is growing gradually. (Light, 2014). The personalized message possesses many benefits and among them, a very important one is, it makes a business to be distinguished from many other competitors as the content is relevant to the audience (O'Reilly, 2014). Customers want to feel special and honored as individuals. They are more likely to build deeper relationships with a

brand when the message is personalized for them and contains strong emotions. (Wong & Yazdanifard, 2015).

Producing quality contents

According to S. Abel (2014), content-based marketing activities need to embrace smart content for achieving the goals. Again, it is best if rather than monotonous routine, contents are produced in diversified routines rather: hire out, partner up, and use voice. (Wong & Yazdanifard, 2015). These traits increase the content's quality. In reality, publishing bad content is better than not publishing at all in many cases.

Understanding obscure demands

A company may always fall into the dilemma of how much information it should include in its contents. Balancing between too much and too little information can always be tricky. Because different groups of people have different demands regarding receiving information. So, identifying these kinds of obscure demands can be a big challenge, because the matter is crucial for them. Świeczak (2012) states that in many cases asserting friendly and efficient influence on buying decisions by giving clients particular, high-quality information is stronger than traditional advertising.

Communicating in the right way

Communication itself has some rules. Different ways of conveying messages can gain the interest of the audience (Wong & Yazdanifard, 2015). Contents should attract consumers to the makers, not the opposite. To bring effectiveness in content making and marketing, companies need to avoid irritating or bore people with their content. While repetition is important for content to be noticed, too much repetition on the other hand can turn out to be extremely negative. Wong & Yazdanifard (2015) stated that, If the same marketer routinely publishes a monotonous style of information format, customers may become uninterested and gradually even disengage from the brand. So, conducting communication in the right way is also crucial for effectiveness in visual content and its marketing.

Encouraging customers' Participation

A study suggests that the ability to engage customers to contribute information to organizations simplifies content exploration (Goldenberg, Oestreicher-Singer & Reichman, 2012). A content published by a company is counted as successful if the number of clicks and shares are high. It is also revealed that 2 factors determined the success of an article (Wylie, 2014). Sharing a company's content is an indication of customers' participation in the company's content marketing as they are like word of mouth in the online world. Again, another research stated that user-generated contents have a good impact on brand equity (Christodoulides, Jevons & Bonhomme, 2012).

Maintaining ethical and trust issues

Customers tend to have more trust in companies that listen to their needs and ideas (Wong & Yazdanifard, 2015). If a company cannot make people trust what they are saying or cannot maintain ethics in the content making, then the saying cannot bring effectiveness in their activities. Syzdek (2014) set a parable that If we assume morals and ethics are at the heart of a marketer, then we may also assume that disclosure and transparency are the veins and arteries that drive business success. Again, another obscure issue is the sensitivity of different people about different things. Sometimes they can be very confusing because it is almost hidden in many cases. But it is sort of like a demand that they do not want to be offended by those

sensitive issues. So, it can be a challenging obscure demand that needs to be identified. Interestingly, the term 'content marketing' is defined as "the art of identifying and understanding the needs of a particular consumer segment and along with that, fulfilling those needs in a skillful method" (Świeczak, 2012).

Attitude towards content marketing (CM)

Content marketing is the only branch of marketing, in which the message in commercial form, has such a strong potential that it makes target consumers look actively for this message (Świeczak, 2012). So, when content marketing is being conducted effectively, the customers' attitude towards it should be positive. This is an indicator of effectiveness in content generation and its marketing.

2.4 Hypotheses

H1: Reaching the right audience has a significant impact on effectiveness.

H2: Bringing personalization has a significant impact on effectiveness.

H3: Producing quality content has a significant impact on effectiveness.

H4: Understanding obscure demands has a significant impact on effectiveness.

H5: Communicating in the right way has a significant impact on effectiveness.

H6: Encouraging customers' participation has a significant impact on effectiveness.

H7: Maintaining ethical and trust issues have a significant impact on effectiveness.

H8: Customers' attitude towards content marketing (CM) has a significant impact on effectiveness.

Figure 2: Research Model

3. Method

3.1 Types of Research Design

This is descriptive research that aims to describe the actual condition of content marketing in Bangladesh. This study tries to draw the real picture of using online visual content as a marketing tool in Bangladesh's perspective. It uses well-known factors associated with online platforms and related marketing tools to get a sufficient understanding of the phenomena.

3.2 Information Needs

As this study tries to explore relatively new phenomena, the required information was mainly primary data. There are very few published and available studies and other relevant data on this topic in the perspective of Bangladesh. So, the research findings are mainly based on primary data. On the other hand, some secondary data related to the topic were also used in developing a literature review. Those provided a more academic and clearer view and understanding of the topic being studied.

3.3 Measurement Instruments

This study uses eight factors to find out the effectiveness of online visual content and its marketing in Bangladesh. They are: reaching the right audience, bringing personalization, producing quality content, understanding obscure demands, communicating in the right way, encouraging customers' participation, maintaining ethical and trust issues, and customers' attitude towards CM.

3.4 Scaling Technique

This study uses a five-point Likert scale to record respondents' views regarding different statements about contents and their marketing in Bangladesh. The five points offered for choosing were: strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, and strongly agree. The respondents were required to choose one of the five points that best expresses his/her opinion regarding each statement. A total of 103 responses were recorded through this scaling technique from the same number of respondents.

3.5 Questionnaire Development

At the beginning of the questionnaire, some demographic information was asked to generate a demographic profile of the respondents. Next, the topic related questions were asked. All the questions of the study were close-ended. For the convenience of the common people, the questionnaire was provided in the native language of Bangladesh – Bengali. As all the respondents were Bangladeshi and many of them often faced difficulty in understanding questionnaires of non-native language, so basically the main questionnaire was translated into Bengali to provide comfort in giving answers. Close-ended questions were chosen because they are befitting with the research. Again, they provide convenience in analysis and coding and use less time to record responses.

3.6 Sampling Technique and Sample Size

To conduct the research, a non-probability sampling technique was used. Because it is convenient, less time consuming, less costly, and befitting with the research plan. Among the non-probability sampling techniques, convenience and judgmental methods were utilized. A total of 103 people participated in the survey and their complete responses were collected accordingly.

3.7 Data Collection

This study is based on primary data collected from respondents of various demographic groups. The technique that is used for that is an online survey. This was posted online for the convenience of the respondents. For collecting data from the respondents, a structured questionnaire was prepared and uploaded online via Google Survey Forms. 5-points Likert scale was used to get the respondents' views regarding a total of 21 statements that were designed to measure the effectiveness of online visual contents and its marketing in Bangladesh. Later when the survey finished, all the responses were gathered in a spreadsheet and saved via Microsoft Excel application to conduct the data analysis part.

3.8 Data Analysis

When the data collection process was finished all the responses were encoded using Microsoft Excel application to make it suitable for further steps. Then the encoded datasheet was transferred in the SPSS application as inputs. IBM SPSS Statistics v.26 was used to conduct data analysis. This study uses a combination of descriptive statistics, correlation, and linear regression to analyze the collected data.\

4. Analysis

Demographic Profile of Respondents

Gender

Among 102 respondents, 80 of them were male which is 78.40%. And, 22 of the respondents were female, which is 21.60%.

Figure 3: Demographic Profile (Gender)

Age Groups

Most of the respondents of this were in the "between 18 to 30" age group (99 respondents). The rest of them were above 30 years old.

Figure 4: Demographic Profile (Age Groups)
Occupation

The majority of the respondents in the survey were students. Among the respondents 94 were students, 5 of them were jobholders, 2 of them were businessmen and the rest 1 fell into the category of other occupations.

Figure 5: Demographic Profile (Occupation)

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 shows that first value of 'Customers' attitude towards CM' has a mean of 4.0784, which is greater than 4. This value means that the majority of the respondents agree that companies should continue to practice content marketing and make good content. Also, 'Awareness' has a mean higher than 4. So, it is also apparent that the majority of the respondents agree that because of content marketing they have become aware of many new companies and their products or services. Here we see 16 items which have means greater than 3, but less than 4. In these cases, the respondents somewhat agree with the statements. The variables are - reachability, matching target groups' interest, positive message, usage of appeals in contents, providing the right information, avoiding sensitive issues, using relevant platforms, balance in repetition, customers' participation, customers' feedback, encouraging customers' communication, ethical contents, trustworthiness, interest, desire, and action. So, the respondents somewhat agree that they can see sufficient amounts of contents of their preferred companies, the contents they see a match with their interests, give them positive messages, use various appeals to attract them, and provide them with the right information. Also, they somewhat agree that companies avoid making contents about sensitive issues, use relevant platforms to display the contents, repeat the contents in a balanced way, encourage customers' participation in content-making, encourage customers' communication with them, give importance to their feedbacks, try not to make unethical contents and maintain trustworthiness in the information provided the contents.

Lastly, they somewhat acknowledge that because of content marketing they have become interested in and desired many new companies' products and services and it also made them purchase many new products or services. Among the items, we also notice 2 items that mean lower than 3, but higher than 2. They are: Relevance and Avoiding making irritating content. So, in these cases, the respondents somewhat disagree with the statements. This implies that they somewhat think that they mostly see irrelevant online visual contents in which they are uninterested and they also see many irritating contents. Only 1 item 'localization' has a mean equal to 3. This indicates that respondents have mixed opinions about the statement. Almost half of them perceive that they only see the contents of those companies that can reach them with their products or services. But the other half of the respondents perceive the opposite.

Table 1 : Descriptive Statistics Analysis

Variables	Items	N	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Reaching the right audience	Relevance	102	1.00	5.00	2.951	1.172
	Localization	102	1.00	5.00	3.000	1.034
	Reachability	102	1.00	5.00	3.226	0.943
Bringing personalization	Matching target groups' interest	102	1.00	5.00	3.216	0.929
Producing quality contents	Positive message	102	1.00	5.00	3.745	0.817
	Usage of appeals in contents	102	1.00	5.00	3.912	0.810
Understanding obscure demands	Providing right information	102	1.00	5.00	3.471	0.887
	Avoiding sensitive issues	102	1.00	5.00	3.510	0.876
Communicating in the right way	Using relevant platforms	102	1.00	5.00	3.461	0.919
	Balance in repetition	102	1.00	5.00	3.304	1.209
	Avoiding making irritative content	102	1.00	5.00	2.863	1.034
Encouraging customers' participation	Customers' participation	102	1.00	5.00	3.677	0.846
	Customers' feedback	102	2.00	5.00	3.677	0.822
	Encouraging customers' communication	102	1.00	5.00	3.755	0.652
Maintaining ethical and trust issues	Ethical contents	102	1.00	5.00	3.441	0.907
	Trustworthiness	102	1.00	5.00	3.069	1.055
Customers' attitude towards CM	Customers' attitude	102	1.00	5.00	4.078	0.754
Effectiveness	Awareness	102	2.00	5.00	4.078	0.592
	Interest	102	1.00	5.00	3.961	0.688
	Desire	102	2.00	5.00	3.961	0.659
	Action	102	1.00	5.00	3.794	0.813
	Valid N (listwise)	102				

Model Summary

Table 2 : Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.670 ^a	.449	.402	.40579

a. Predictors: (Constant), Customers_attitude, personalization, ethical_and_trust_issues, quality_contents, obscure_demands, encourage_customers_participation, communicate_in_right_way, right_audience

Here the R-value is 0.670 (67%). This indicates that the independent variables have moderate positive linking with the dependent variable (effectiveness). And the R square value is 0.449. This value indicates that a 44.90% variation of the dependent variable can be explained by the independent variables.

ANOVA

Table 3 : ANOVA

ANOVA ^a						
	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	12.479	8	1.560	9.473	.000 ^b
	Residual	15.314	93	.165		
	Total	27.792	101			

a. Dependent Variable: Effectiveness

b. Predictors: (Constant), Customers_attitude, personalization, ethical_and_trust_issues, quality_contents, obscure_demands, encourage_customers_participation, communicate_in_right_way, right_audience

The ANOVA table indicates that independent variables have a significant impact on the dependent variable, $F(8,93) = 9.473$, $p = 0.000$.

Coefficients

Table 4 shows that 3 of the independent variables – ‘Producing quality contents’, ‘Understanding obscure demands’, and ‘Customers’ attitude towards CM’ are significant (p -value < 0.05), and the rest of the variables are not significant (p -value > 0.05). So, these 3 variables have a significant impact on the effectiveness and the rest of the variables do not have a significant impact on effectiveness. So, it can be claimed that a change in the quality of contents that the companies produce, a change in the companies’ ability to understand the customers’ obscure demands, and a change in the customers’ attitude towards content marketing as a whole will significantly affect the effectiveness of online visual contents and its marketing in Bangladesh. So, hypothesis h3, h4, and h8 are accepted. On the other hand, h1, h2, h5, h6, and h7 are rejected. We also notice that all of the significant variables have positive coefficient values. So, ‘quality contents’, ‘obscure demands’, and ‘customers attitude’ have a positive relationship with the dependent variable – ‘effectiveness’. Hence, an increase in these factors will also increase effectiveness. Again, from the above data table we can derive the following formula (only considering the significant variables):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Effectiveness} = & 1.531 + 0.179 * (\text{Quality Contents}) \\ & + 0.267 * (\text{Obscure Demands}) \\ & + 0.277 * (\text{Customers' Attitude}) \end{aligned}$$

*** only considering the significant variables

$$Y = b_0 + b_1 * x_1 + b_2 * x_2 + b_3 * x_3$$

Here, Y = Dependent Variable, b = Coefficient, and x = Independent Variable. So, the analysis indicates that if the companies can increase the production of good quality content, better

understand the obscure demands of the customers and increase the customers' positive attitude towards content marketing, then the effectiveness of their content marketing will increase. As the other factors are not significant, we cannot claim such for those.

Table 4 : Coefficients

Model		Coefficients ^a				t	Sig.
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Beta		
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	1.531	.384			3.984	.000
	Reaching the right audience	.086	.066	.133		1.299	.197
	Bringing personalization	-.004	.055	-.008		-.078	.938
	Producing quality contents	.179	.075	.209		2.390	.019
	Understanding obscure demands	.267	.070	.358		3.804	.000
	Communicating in the right way	-.123	.073	-.172		-1.685	.095
	Encouraging customers' participation	-.020	.096	-.020		-.214	.831
	Maintaining ethical and trust issues	-.034	.061	-.053		-.548	.585
	Customers' attitude towards CM	.277	.061	.398		4.564	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Effectiveness

Conclusion

Using content to easily catch the attention of Internet users as a marketing tool is becoming popular. Along with the developed countries and their business organizations, Bangladeshi local and multinational companies are also trying their best to utilize Internet platforms. As these platforms offer easy access methods and possess a vast opportunity to bring creativity in marketing, content marketing has become an obligatory portion of the marketing strategies. Marketers all around the world understand the power that visual contents have when it comes

to attract and engage the common people. Hence, the visual contents have become the chief component of the marketing messages. This story-telling type of marketing has reached a whole new level by dint of content marketing. And people always like to be a part of good stories. The study about contents and its marketing has provided some notable insights from the perspective of Bangladesh. Even though sometimes people get irritated by the contents' appearance, they acknowledge that visual contents attract them. Through content marketing, they came to know about products or service offerings that they never heard of before. But they also gave a message. They informed us that like every powerful tool, sometimes marketers misuse content marketing. That is hampering their overall experience with it.

Recommendations and limitations

This research was done on a topic that is extremely important to both businesses and scholars. It can give useful suggestions for future study, on the one hand, and significant insights for Bangladeshi content marketers, on the other hand. We provide a few suggestions for additional investigation. First, because internet material may irritate viewers, it might provide biased or unfavorable information that does not correspond to reality. As a result, while selecting samples, researchers should be as cautious as possible. Second, researchers should conduct surveys over a longer period of time to examine this or comparable problems. Third, because individuals from all walks of life are continually exposed to online information and the internet, and because cellphones are accessible to the overwhelming majority of the population, researchers should not limit themselves to a small group of upper-class and/or educated people. Fourth, because the number of studies on this topic is insufficient to allow for broad-scale research, personnel brief interviews may be more appropriate than typical online surveys for obtaining more accurate primary data.

For businessmen, the advice is as follows: first, content marketers should place a greater emphasis on content quality rather than quantity. Second, in order to ensure optimal personalisation in content publication, market segmentation should be as precise as feasible. Second, customers' hidden or cryptic desires for the company's contents must be recognized and met. Fourth, content creators must avoid cheap techniques that provide short-term profits but negatively impact clients' perceptions of their marketing. For instance, ridiculing a certain group of individuals to amuse others. Fifth, to make material more interesting, content creators might use advertising appeals and similar themes. Finally, positive messages delivered through content, even if unrelated to the company's products or services, can be effective provided public reactions are appropriately monitored.

This study, like all others, has its own set of limitations. First, there was a paucity of earlier studies in this sector, which may have aided us by establishing a firm foundation for our investigation. However, just a few studies have been undertaken in this area. As a result, the absence of appropriate empirical data was a source of worry throughout the investigation. Second, because the study was conducted at a difficult period in which the country was shaken by the COVID-19 epidemic, it was difficult to achieve excellent variation in the sample group. Third, the amount of time allotted for the study was quite restricted. As a result, it cannot be stated that a more well-organized research strategy was not conceivable. Fourth, there is a shortage of one or more generally approved standards.

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